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ABSTRACT

Man and woman are gifted with equal rational capacity, with women constituting half of the world's population. Women have played many different roles in society and possess various strengths such as good listening and communication skills, flexibility to compromise, extensive experience in practical problem-solving, and caring for people. The presence of women is a crucial element in fostering and maintaining the local population. Elevating the health status of women is vital to improving the health of the entire community. Premenstrual syndrome (PMS) can be debilitating and negatively impact the quality of life (QOL) of those affected. Physical symptoms such as headaches, breast tenderness, swelling, abdominal bloating, heaviness, low energy, fatigue, back, and muscle pain are common.

Relaxing one's muscles has been found to significantly reduce anxiety. Jacobson (1929), Lang, Melamed, Hart (1970), and Mohan and Chopra (1985) found that certain personality dimensions such as neuroticism and anxiety, which can create stress in women suffering from premenstrual tension, could be successfully reduced with the help of relaxation therapy. It is essential as a yoga practitioner to help individuals conserve their energy and physical and mental fitness through proper yoga interventions.

Keywords: *PMS (Premenstrual Syndrome), Yoga Intervention, Relaxation Techniques*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The period of adolescence, spanning from ages 10 to 19, is a crucial phase in one's life and makes up over 20% of the world's population. In India, the youth population amounts to around 327 million, representing 30% of the country's population, with this number expected to continue growing. Despite this, there remains a general lack of understanding of the unique needs of Indian adolescents, particularly adolescent girls, who are a vulnerable group due to limited access to basic healthcare, education, and sexual and reproductive health services. Cultural beliefs and traditions surrounding menstruation in India can also perpetuate misconceptions and stigma.

Research studies conducted by Mahajan and Sharma (2004), Bhan et al. (2004), and Gupta et al. (2006) suggest that many adolescent girls in India have limited knowledge about reproductive health and menstruation. Empowering adolescent girls through appropriate education can be an effective means of enabling them to manage the demands and challenges of everyday life. However, health education that incorporates theory-based behavior change strategies is not widely available in many developing countries. As such, the researcher sought to address this gap by developing a yoga intervention program to educate adolescent girls about menstrual hygiene, premenstrual syndrome, and its management. Such interventions have the potential to positively impact the development of India's promising youth population.

MENSTRUATION

Menstruation, or menses, is a monthly occurrence in sexually mature females (Muktananda, 2003) that involves a sequence of events. The menstrual cycle (MC) is measured from the first day of bleeding to the first day of the next period and typically lasts 28 days, with 23-35 days being considered normal. The MC is divided into pre- and post-ovulatory periods, and it consists of three phases: the follicular phase, which lasts for 10-14 days from day one of the cycle before ovulation; the luteal phase, which is associated with peak progesterone secretion; and the post-ovulatory period,

which lasts for 14 days. The pre-ovulatory stage can vary between 2-3 days and may be further delayed due to complex psychophysiological dysfunctions.

Premenstrual syndrome (PMS) is a term used to describe a group of emotional, mental, and physical symptoms that affect women in the days leading up to their menstrual period. PMS is prevalent in the early stages of adolescence, and around 75% of women in their reproductive age experience symptoms related to the premenstrual phase of the MC (Johnson et al., 1988). PMS symptoms include fluid retention, mood changes, depression, weight gain, urinary tract infection, breathlessness, nasal congestion, headaches, susceptibility to conjunctivitis, and others. While the exact cause of PMS is unknown, it is thought to be related to hormonal imbalances.

According to the World Health Organization's International Statistical Classification of Disease and Related problems, 10th revision (ICD-10), PMS is often classified under the generic term Premenstrual syndrome, which is listed in the International Statistical Classification of diseases and Related Health Problems, 10th revision (ICD-10). While PMS may be a socially constructed disorder, it is a collection of more than 200 different symptoms, with irritability, tension, and dysphonia being the most prominent (Rodin et al., 1992).

Healthcare professionals can help create awareness among women about comprehensive measures to reduce PMS during their childbearing age. This, in turn, can prevent the negative impact on the quality of life of women. It is believed that relaxing one's muscles greatly reduces anxiety (Jacobson, 1929; Lang, Melamed, & Hart, 1970), and certain personality dimensions such as neuroticism and anxiety that can create stress in women suffering from premenstrual tension could be successfully reduced with relaxation therapy (Mohan & Chopra, 1985).

METHOD

Qualitative studies were included in the review. Based on the objectives of the current review, inclusion and exclusion criteria were prepared, and based on that, various data base was used in the selection of studies. The collected studies were checked for clarity and content and then used for the review.

Criteria for Sample Selection

For the selection of the sample, two criteria were employed: the inclusion criterion and the exclusion criterion.

Table 1: Criteria for Participant Selection: A Comprehensive Overview

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Adult women of reproductive age (20-45 years).• Willing to participate and extend their co-operation for the study.• Who are literates• Ready to give written consent for the intervention.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Adult women above the age of 45 years and less than 20 years.• Pregnant and lactating mothers .• Who have undergone hysterectomy.• Who are illiterates .• Who have not given the written consent .• Who are severely anaemic.

Electronic Database Searching The Databases Searched

PubMed, online journal, Access open, Google Scholar

Keywords Used

Premenstrual syndrome, yoga intervention, mechanism Relaxation techniques, qualitative Research.

Data Extraction and Quality Assessment

The article selection process utilized the PRISMA flow diagram, and eligibility criteria were applied to extracted data. Studies that met the criteria were evaluated for relevance, appropriateness, clarity, and methodology, while those that did not were excluded. The review process involved two independent reviewers assessing the selected articles, with the extracted data including details such as participant information, year of publication, study method, type of intervention, and outcome.

ANALYSIS

Steps in the analysis

- **Step I:** Obtain data were tabulated and classified as author. Study design, year of publication, setting, method, sample size, type of intervention, components of intervention and outcome.
- **Step II:** Identifying the findings of the studies. The studies were identified with their setting, method, and sample size, type of intervention and component of intervention.
- **Step III:** Categorizing the findings. Finding were categorized under the headings of coping education coping on autistic parents or mothers only.

RESULTS

In the review study, a total of 250 articles were initially identified as potentially relevant. However, after careful screening, it was found that 200 articles were duplicates, 25 articles did not meet the inclusion criteria, and 13 articles did not provide information on the intervention. Consequently, only 5 studies met the criteria and were included in the review.

Characteristic of the Articles

The review comprised five studies, all of which were qualitative in nature. The hospital setting was the predominant site of these studies, which were published between 2010 and 2020. .

Table 2

Study/ Author	Year of publication	Research Design	No. of Participants	Sample Characteristic	Theme	Sub-theme
1. Karthiga ,Abhijit Boratne	2010	Cross-sectional	1.193 girls with dysmennorrh ea.	Girls in pondicherry.	1.Study on menstrual problems and pattern of consultation among adolescent school girls in Pondicherry,	1.1. There is an urgent need for strong health educational activities among the adolescent girls, 2.1. urgent need for strong health educational activities among their parents and teachers for effective management of menstrualproblems among all adolescent girls. 3.2

2. Patil and Wasnik Wadke	2014	OBSERVATI ONAL	61	females with dysmenorrhea	1. Health problems amongst adolescent girls in rural areas of Maharashtra 2. majority of the girls had one or the other problems related to their menstrual problems	Subtheme 1. adolescent girls and more than 50% of the study subjects had one or the other symptoms of PMS.
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Table 2: Contd.,

3. Choi, Lee, Lehert	2014	Review	80	23 females documented symptoms, the most predominant symptoms were joint-muscle-back pain, abdominal pain and irritability.	1. Impact of premenstrual symptoms on activities of daily life in Korean women 2. ADL were significantly associated with the severity of PMS	<u>Subtheme</u> 1. Most of the women (91.5%) had no knowledge regarding terminology pertaining to PMS. 2. There was a high correlation between the duration and severity of Symptoms
4. Heinemann, Minh	2016	A Brief Review	N - 60	Review based study	1. Impact of severe premenstrual disorders on work absenteeism and productivity 2. Employed women with moderate-to-severe PMS/PMDD had higher rate of productivity impairment	1. Outcomes were obtained for impairment of working productivity or efficiency using the premenstrual symptoms screening tool.

5.	Dennerstein, Lehert	2014	cross sectional study	59	59 Females with menstruation related issues.	1. Problem related to menstruation among medical students at Rewa. 2. Maximum number of student does not seek medical advice and self treatment	1. These conditions influence women's lives, relationships, work and is the most common reason for absenteeism for women younger than age 30
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CONCLUSIONS

The prevalence of menstrual disorders among adolescent girls is evident, with estimates ranging from 30% to 87%. The available treatment options include medical (such as hormonal, anti-depressant, and painkiller medications) and surgical (hysterectomy and salpingo-oophorectomy) therapies, as well as alternative medical treatments. However, these medical and surgical approaches often come with side effects. Therefore, alternative therapies, such as exercise or physical activity, are recommended, according to Stevinson and Ernst (2001) and Rapkin (2003).

It is apparent that women with premenstrual tension syndrome (PMTS) experience psychological and behavioral changes that can significantly impact their lives. Consequently, psychotherapeutic techniques are becoming increasingly important in treating women with PMTS. The literature shows that various psychotherapeutic techniques can be useful in addressing PMTS symptoms.

Based on the above discussion, it is evident that the most common PMTS symptoms are anger, irritability, anxiety, tiredness, and difficulty concentrating. PMTS is a prevalent issue that affects women's daily living activities, highlighting the need for proper attention and treatment protocols with minimal side effects that are easy to implement.

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